

Mechanistic studies of substitution reaction of *trans*-(diaqua)-(*N,N'*-ethylene-bis-salicylamide)chromium(III) ion

S. C. Dash^a, K. C. Behera, N. N. Dash^b, R. R. Jha^c and P. Mohanty^{a*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Utkal University, Bhubaneswar-751 004, Orissa, India

E-mail : saratchandradash@rediffmail.com

^bDepartment of Chemistry, North Orissa University, Baripada, Orissa, India

^cDepartment of Chemistry, Ranchi University, Ranchi-834 008, Jharkhand, India

Manuscript received 8 october 2009, revised 8 February 2010, accepted 16 March 2010

Abstract : The kinetics of substitution of *trans*-[Cr(Salm)(OH)₂]⁺ with some biologically important ligands (Nu⁻) viz. glycine (Gly), *p*-aminobenzoic acid (Paba), glycyL-glycine (Gly-gly), L-histidine (His), L-isoleucine (Ile) has been studied spectrophotometrically over the range : 25 ≤ *t* ≤ 45 °C, 1.8 ≤ pH ≤ 5.5, 0.01 ≤ [Nucleophile] ≤ 0.30, *I* = 0.5 mol dm⁻³ (KNO₃). Although there are two replaceable aqua ligands in the complex, only mono substitution occurred, which is evident from Job's curve. The kinetic studies also showed one aqua ligand substitution. Unlike *trans*-[Cr(Salen)(OH)₂]⁺, the rates of aqua ligand substitution were found slower indicating moderate labilization of axial aqua ligand. The reaction takes place via an outersphere association between the Cr^{III} complex and various nucleophiles followed by transformation of the outer into inner sphere complexes by slow interchange. The anation rate constants (10⁴ k_{an}/s⁻¹) at 25 °C were found to be 14.98 (Gly), 8.45 (Ile), 10.52 (Paba), 14.23 (His) and 13.78 (Gly-gly) and the corresponding Δ*H*[‡] (kJ mol⁻¹) values are 57.7 ± 1.6, 38.3 ± 1.3, 43.0 ± 0.8, 34.2 ± 2.7 and 39.7 ± 3.1, the Δ*S*[‡] (JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹) values are -105 ± 5, -175 ± 5, -157 ± 3, -65.8 ± 9 and -166 ± 11. The higher value of the k_{an} in comparison to k_{ex} and highly negative values of activation entropy and variation of k_{an} by changing nucleophiles, support I_a mechanism for the substitution reactions.

Keywords : Substitution reaction, chromium(III), mechanism, ligand, kinetic.

Introduction

Studies on Schiff bases and their metal complexes is an active area of research, due to their catalytic activities in biological and chemical processes¹⁻¹⁰. The transition metal complexes containing Schiff bases are well known homogeneous catalysts for various industrially and environmentally important organic transformations which led to many recent studies⁵⁻¹⁰. Very often these complexes are immobilised or embedded on various solid inorganic/organic supports for heterogenisation of homogeneous catalyst to get the combined advantages of both heterogeneous and homogeneous catalysts^{11,12}.

Schiff base complexes of Cr^{III} have received considerable attention because of high catalytic activity, interaction and oxidative cleavage of DNA/protein, apoptotic cell death due to DNA damage etc.^{1-10,13-15}. The factors contributing to the structure and anomalous substitutional reactivity of Schiff base complexes of chromium(III) has been sparsely studied^{16,17}. H₂Salm, a potential quadridentate ligand, can undergo multiple stages of deprotonation

to yield species of varying charges from 0 to -2 at different pH. On coordination to Cr^{III}, it is expected to enhance lability of Cr^{III}-OH₂ bond as has been observed previously with oxalate (ox), nitrilotriacetate (nta), ethylenediaminetetracetate (edta) and *N,N'*-ethylene-bis-salicylideneimine (salen) etc.¹⁶⁻²⁰. Enhance lability of Cr^{III}-OH₂ bond may change the mechanism from I_a to I_d.

In continuation of our earlier study²¹, the results of substitutional behaviour of coordinated water in *trans*-[Cr(Salm)(OH)₂]⁺ towards a series of biologically important molecules have been presented here.

Acid dissociation constant of [Cr(Salm)(OH)₂]⁺ :

The dissociation constant for the aqua ligand in the title complex was measured potentiometrically which gives only one inflexion point in the pH range 6 to 11 attributing the dissociation of H⁺ from one aqua ligand (eq. (1)). The dissociation constant (p*K*_d), derived using the pH data, was found to be 8.85 ± 0.3 at 27 °C which is comparable with the value (8.97 ± 0.1 at 25 °C) reported for its corresponding H₂Salen of analogue¹⁷.

Kinetic measurements :

The kinetics of substitution on $[\text{Cr}(\text{Salm})(\text{OH}_2)_2]^+$ with different nucleophiles were followed in the range of temperature 25–45 °C, pH = 1.8–5.5 and $I = 0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (KNO_3). Reaction progress was monitored spectrophotometrically at $\lambda = 335\text{--}340 \text{ nm}$, with pseudo-first order conditions maintained for each run. The $[\text{H}^+]$ of the solutions were adjusted using HNO_3 and NaOH . Rate constants (k_{obs}) and other parameters were computed using suitable computer programs.

Results and discussion

The absorption spectra of title complex with different nucleophiles (after keeping for 3 h at 25 °C) showed an increase of absorbance, especially in between 300–350 nm, indicating the interaction of nucleophiles with $[\text{Cr}(\text{Salm})(\text{OH}_2)_2]^+$ (Fig. 1). As the reaction progresses, the absorbance values decreased. Although there are two

Fig. 1. Spectral changes in the reaction between *trans*- $[\text{Cr}(\text{Salm})(\text{OH}_2)_2]^+$ and glycyglycine at different intervals (pH = 4.05, $t = 25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $I = 0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$): (1) $[\text{gly-gly}] = 2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; (2–6) $[\text{Cr}^{\text{III}} \text{ complex}] = 4 \times 10^{-4}$ and $[\text{gly-gly}] = 2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ recorded at 0.5, 6, 25, 45 and 65 min, respectively.

replaceable aqua ligands in the complex, only mono substitution occurred as also evident from Job's curve which showed only one maxima at 0.5 mole fractions (X_1)'s of Cr^{III} complex (Figs. 2a and 2b). Mono-substitution of aqua ligand has also been established from equilibrium measurements with several similar Cr^{III} complexes^{16,17}.

Fig. 2a. Job's curve for the anation of $[\text{Cr}(\text{Salm})(\text{OH}_2)_2]^+$ with glycinate ion.

Fig. 2b. Job's curve for the anation of $[\text{Cr}(\text{Salm})(\text{OH}_2)_2]^+$ with glycyglycinate ion.

Kinetics of anation :

Preliminary experiments of anation reactions were conducted with fixed $[\text{Nu}]_T (= 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}; \text{Nu} = \text{entering nucleophile})$ and varying $[\text{Cr}(\text{Salm})(\text{OH}_2)_2]^+$ (2.0×10^{-4} to $7.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$), keeping the pH and other parameters constant, yielded practically constant values of rate constants. This suggests a first order dependence of the reaction rate on $[\text{Cr}^{\text{III}}]_T$. The rate law is given by eq. (2),

$$\text{Rate} = k_{\text{obs}} [\text{Cr}(\text{Salm})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^+_T \quad (2)$$

Fig. 3 indicates the variation of k_{obs} , for the formation of $[\text{Cr}(\text{Salm})(\text{OH}_2)(\text{glyH})]$ from $[\text{Cr}(\text{Salm})(\text{OH}_2)_2]^+$ at varying pH and different glycine concentration. At different

Fig. 3. The plots of k_{obs} versus $[\text{gly}]_T$ for the anation of glycine in $[\text{Cr}(\text{Salm})(\text{OH}_2)_2]^+$ at 25 °C and varying pH : 2.71 (1), 2.91 (2), 3.14 (3), 3.65 (4) and 4.4 (5).

pH, k_{obs} showed a non-linear dependence on $[\text{gly}]_T$ with practically zero intercept indicating that the backward reaction is insignificant under the experimental conditions. The plots of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $[\text{gly}]_T^{-1}$ were straight lines (Fig. 5, $r^2 > 0.98$). Under the pH range studied, the title complex exists in diaqua form, $[\text{Cr}(\text{Salm})(\text{OH}_2)_2]^+$ ($K_d = 1.41 \times 10^{-9}$) while glycine ($\text{NH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-COOH}$) will exist in both $\text{NH}_3^+\text{-CH}_2\text{-COOH}$ (HA^+) and $\text{NH}_3^+\text{-CH}_2\text{-COO}^-$ (A) forms ($K_{a_1} = 4.47 \times 10^{-3}$ and $K_{\text{NH}_3^+} = 1.66 \times 10^{-10}$ at 25 °C) as depicted in eq. (3).

Keeping these facts in view, the following reaction scheme is suggested.

Scheme 1

For which

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{(k_1 Q_1 [\text{H}^+] + k_2 K_a Q_2) [\text{HA}]_T}{[\text{H}^+] + K_a + (Q_1 [\text{H}^+] + Q_2 K_a) [\text{HA}]_T} \quad (4)$$

This can be rewritten as (5), where, A and B are defined in eqs. (6) and (7),

$$\frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \left(\frac{[\text{H}^+] + K_a}{A} \right) \times \left(\frac{1}{[\text{HA}]_T} \right) + \frac{B}{A} \quad (5)$$

$$A = k_1 Q_1 [\text{H}^+] + k_2 K_a Q_2 \quad (6)$$

$$B = Q_1 [\text{H}^+] Q_2 K_a \quad (7)$$

Since the plots of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $[\text{gly}]_T^{-1}$ at varying pH result practically constant intercepts (B/A), it is reasonable to assume that rates of formation of $[\text{Cr}(\text{OH}_2)\text{A}]$ from outer-sphere complexes involving HA^+ ($\text{NH}_3^+\text{-CH}_2\text{-COOH}$) and A ($\text{NH}_3^+\text{-CH}_2\text{-COO}^-$) are identical i.e. $k_1 = k_2$. Any differences in rate constant would be relatively small and difficult to distinguish by the procedure employed. The same was applied for the anation reaction of $\text{H}_3\text{PO}_4/\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4^-$ and $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4\text{H}^-/\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ with $\text{Cr}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{OH}_2)^{3+}$, where it was concluded that within experimental error the rate constants for interchange were identical. The plots of A, derived from the slopes of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $[\text{gly}]_T^{-1}$ plots, against corresponding $[\text{H}^+]$ was straight line as shown in Fig. 4. The values of anation rate constant, k_{an} (here $k_1 = k_2$) and the outer-sphere association constants, Q_1 and Q_2 were derived using eqs. (5) and (6). For glycine anation, the values of k_{an} , Q_1 and Q_2 are found to be $15.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$, 1.13 and $4.49 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$, respectively. The values of Q_1 and Q_2 are comparable with those reported for outer-sphere association constant ($1.9 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$, at 30 °C) for the interaction of a $[\text{Cr}(\text{Salen})(\text{OH}_2)_2]^+$ with pyridine-3-carboxylate ion¹⁷ Since the values of Q_1 and Q_2 are more or less in the same order and it is assumed $k_1 = k_2$ with reasonable

Fig. 4. Dependence of constant A, defined in eq. (5), on $[H^+]$ for the anation of glycine with $[Cr(Salm)(OH_2)_2]^+$ at 25 °C.

accuracy, the rate may be analysed with a much simpler reaction scheme as depicted in eqs. (8–10).

where, HA and A^- represent the carboxylic acid and carboxylate forms of nucleophiles used in this study.

The anation rate of $[Cr(Salm)(OH_2)_2]^+$ for different ligands at varying pH with fixed $[Nu^-]_T$ are presented in Table 1. The dissociation constants (K_{a1} , 25 °C) for the release of H^+ from -COOH of L-isoleucine, glycyl-glycine, L-histidine, *p*-aminobenzoic acid and glycine are reported to be 4.17×10^{-5} , 4.90×10^{-6} , 9.34×10^{-8} and 6.23×10^{-6} , respectively^{20,22}. Since the reactions have been studied at pH = 7.5, the participation of the conjugate base of $[Cr(Salm)(OH_2)_2]^+$ ($K_d = 1.41 \times 10^{-9}$ at 27 °C) in the substitution reaction is less likely. Thus under experimental pH range, the change of rate with increase of pH is primarily due to increase in [conjugate base] from the nucleophiles. Keeping these in view the rate law based on eqs. (8–10) is given by eq. (11),

$$k_{obs} = \frac{k_{an}K_{OS}K_{a1}[Nu]_T}{[H^+] + K_{a1} + K_{OS}K_{a1}[Nu]_T} \quad (11)$$

which can be rearranged to eq. (12),

$$k_{obs}^{-1} = k_{an}^{-1} + \frac{([H^+] + K_{a1})}{k_{an}K_{OS}K_{a1}} \times [Nu]_T^{-1} \quad (12)$$

Table 1. Rate constants for substitution of $[Cr(Salm)(OH_2)_2]^+$ by different nucleophiles at 25.0 ± 0.1 °C, $I = 0.5$ mol dm^{-3} (KNO_3), $[Cr(Salm)]_T = 2.0 \times 10^{-4}$ mol dm^{-3} , 2% (v/v) MeOH-H₂O medium^a

[Nucleophile] _T (mol dm^{-3})	Gly	Ile	Paba	His	Gly-gly
			$10^4 k_{obs}$ (s^{-1}) ^b		
0.01	0.52 ± 0.07 (0.52)	0.42 ± 0.04 (0.45)	0.62 ± 0.04 (0.60)	0.49 ± 0.05 (0.53)	0.52 ± 0.04 (0.51)
0.02	1.08 ± 0.06 (1.02)	0.54 ± 0.07 (0.52)	1.13 ± 0.07 (1.13)	0.65 ± 0.10 (0.77)	0.98 ± 0.05 (1.01)
0.03	1.52 ± 0.06 (1.65)	0.76 ± 0.10 (0.85)	1.59 ± 0.15 (1.64)	0.94 ± 0.08 (1.01)	1.54 ± 0.10 (1.44)
0.04	1.93 ± 0.06 (1.93)	0.99 ± 0.09 (0.99)	1.99 ± 0.11 (2.04)	1.23 ± 0.02 (1.21)	1.81 ± 0.11 (1.86)
0.05	2.27 ± 0.08 (2.34)	1.18 ± 0.06 (1.23)	2.24 ± 0.18 (2.43)	1.41 ± 0.14 (1.46)	2.17 ± 0.15 (2.24)
0.06	2.63 ± 0.07 (2.73)	1.39 ± 0.11 (1.41)	2.71 ± 0.19 (2.78)	1.69 ± 0.18 (1.76)	2.56 ± 0.11 (2.61)
0.07	2.92 ± 0.11 (3.10)	1.52 ± 0.12 (1.63)	3.24 ± 0.22 (3.10)	2.09 ± 0.12 (2.22)	3.14 ± 0.12 (2.96)
0.10	3.96 ± 0.09 (4.12)	2.03 ± 0.26 (2.14)	4.26 ± 0.26 (3.91)	2.58 ± 0.22 (2.69)	3.94 ± 0.18 (3.88)
0.15	5.31 ± 0.10 (5.53)	2.97 ± 0.17 (2.86)	5.47 ± 0.21 (4.91)	3.89 ± 0.26 (3.66)	5.15 ± 0.13 (5.11)
0.20	6.65 ± 0.16 (6.66)	3.50 ± 0.09 (3.44)	6.29 ± 0.32 (5.62)	4.86 ± 0.23 (4.45)	6.17 ± 0.16 (6.09)
0.25	7.31 ± 0.21 (7.60)	4.01 ± 0.15 (3.93)	6.87 ± 0.30 (6.16)	5.63 ± 0.26 (5.13)	7.31 ± 0.18 (6.88)
0.30	7.79 ± 0.13 (8.39)	4.59 ± 0.33 (4.40)	7.71 ± 0.32 (6.60)	6.35 ± 0.31 (5.70)	7.75 ± 0.22 (7.26)

^apH, 2.91 ± 0.03 (Gly); 3.00 ± 0.02 (Ile); 2.90 ± 0.03 (Paba); 3.02 ± 0.02 (His); 3.60 ± 0.03 (Gly-gly).

^bValues in the parenthesis are calculated $10^4 k$ (s^{-1}). Gly = glycine, Ile = isoleucine, Paba = *p*-aminobenzoic acid; His = Histidine; Gly-gly = Glycyl-glycine.

The values of k_{an} and K_{OS} at 25 °C, derived from intercepts and slopes of $1/k_{obs}$ versus $[Nu]_T^{-1}$ plots (Fig. 5), for anation of glycine are $15.76 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and 4.39 dm^3

Fig. 5. Plots of $1/k_{obs}$ versus $[gly]_T^{-1}$ at varying temperature : (1) 25 °C, (2) 30 °C, (3) 35 °C, (4) 40 °C, (5) 45 °C.

mol^{-1} . These values compare well with those derived using the reaction (Scheme 1) indicating the rate data (k_{obs}) at any fixed pH would be sufficient to derive k_{an} and K_{OS} values with reasonable accuracy. Keeping this in view, the rates of anation were studied at fixed pH with varying concentrations of nucleophiles and temperatures (25–40 °C). The rate constants (k_{obs}) for the anation of different nucleophiles were collected in Table 2. The values of k_{an} and K_{OS} , derived using eqs. (8–10), are collected in Table 3.

It is well known that $[Cr(OH_2)_6]^{3+}$ is substitution inert. The reactivity towards substitution is, however, greatly enhanced (10^2 to 10^5 times faster) by replacing some of the aqua ligands by polydentate ligands like edta, nta, meso-tetrakis(*p*-sulphonatophenyl)porphine (tpps) *etc.* mainly due to labilization of axial aqua ligand. It is worthwhile to note that anation rates (k_{an}) of various nucleophiles at $[Cr(\text{Salm})(OH_2)_2]^+$ are substantially lower than those obtained with corresponding salen complex (0.15 – $0.53 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, 30 °C for anation of thiocyanate ion, azide ion, pyridine, imidazole and nicotinic acid)²¹ but comparable with the formation *trans*- $[Cr(\text{naphprn})(N_3)(H_2O)]$ {naphprn = *N,N'*-trimethylenebis-(naphthylideneimine)} from its corresponding di-aqua complex in mildly acidic

Table 2. Effect of pH on the rate of substitution of $[Cr(\text{Salm})(OH_2)_2]^+$ by different nucleophiles at 27.0 ± 0.1 °C. $I = 0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (KNO_3), $[Cr(\text{Salm})(OH_2)_2]^+_T = 2.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ in 2% (v/v) MeOH- H_2O medium, $[nucleophile]_T = 0.10 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

Nucleophiles	pH	$10^4 k_{obs} (\text{s}^{-1})$
Gly	3.12	3.89 ± 0.12
	3.31	4.21 ± 0.07
	3.80	4.52 ± 0.11
	4.22	4.92 ± 0.08
	4.80	5.29 ± 0.09
Gly-gly	5.50	5.48 ± 0.14
	3.21	3.67 ± 0.13
	3.63	3.87 ± 0.11
	4.11	4.31 ± 0.13
	4.92	5.11 ± 0.06
Paba	5.51	5.31 ± 0.12
	1.82	3.82 ± 0.18
	2.05	3.98 ± 0.07
	2.50	4.14 ± 0.12
	2.90	4.26 ± 0.08
His	3.11	2.03 ± 0.05
	3.29	2.25 ± 0.08
	3.61	2.45 ± 0.12
	3.79	2.82 ± 0.11
	3.96	3.21 ± 0.09
Ile	2.61	1.23 ± 0.09
	2.82	1.61 ± 0.14
	3.01	1.96 ± 0.12
	3.32	2.37 ± 0.11
	3.51	2.59 ± 0.08

medium)¹⁶. In general substitution reaction at $[Cr(OH_2)_6]^{3+}$ is believed to proceed by an associative interchange (I_a) mechanism. However, the reaction may be either I_d or I_a , if one or more aqua ligand are replaced by other ligands. Usually the k_{an} values are compared with water exchange rate constant at $[Cr(OH_2)_6]^{3+}$ for prediction of I_d or I_a mechanism valid for the reaction. The much higher values of k_{an} compared to the isotopic water exchange rate constant of $[Cr(OH_2)_6]^{3+}$ (4.17×10^{-6})²² supports an I_a mechanism for the anation reaction of $[Cr(\text{Salm})(OH_2)_2]^+$ with various nucleophiles.

A comparative anation rate constant (k_{an}), outer-sphere association constant (K_{OS}) along with activation parameters for different nucleophiles at (aqua)chromium(III) centre are collected in Table 3. It is evident that both k_{an}

Table 3. Comparison of anation rate constants (k_{an}), outer sphere complex formation constants (K_{OS}) and activation parameters for the anation reaction of $[\text{Cr}(\text{Salm})(\text{OH}_2)_2]^+$ with that of other aqua Cr^{III} systems

System (Metal centre/nucleophile) ^a	$10^4 k_{an}$ (s ⁻¹)	K_{OS}	ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS^\ddagger (JK mol ⁻¹)	Refs
$[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}/\text{H}_2\text{O}^*$	0.024 (25 °C)	–	108.6	11.6	22
$[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}/\text{gly}$	(3.34–6.8) (35 °C)	–	51.9	–42.7	23
$[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}/\text{ala}$	0.58 (35 °C)	–	64.9	–113.6	24, 25
$[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}/\text{val}$	2.34 (25 °C)	3.29 ± 0.1	90.4	–21.0	24, 25
$[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}/\text{L-ornithine}$	1.70 (40 °C)	18.9	55.8	-138 ± 17	26
$[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}/\text{hydroxyproline}$	1.00 (40 °C)	–	72.9	–98.2	24, 25
$[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}/\text{tryptophan}$	1.17 (40 °C)	–	65.6	–112.4	24, 25
$[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}/\text{methionine}$	2.22 (35 °C)	–	61.1	–116.3	24, 25
$[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}/\text{glutamine}$	1.81 (40 °C)	–	52.0	–150.6	24, 25
$[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}/\text{pyc-3}$	10.2 (35 °C)	5.42	–	–	27
$[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}/\text{phenylalanine}$	13.8 (35 °C)	–	53.6	–141.7	24, 25
$[\text{Cr}(\text{Salm})(\text{OH}_2)_2]^+/\text{Imz}$	9.51 (25 °C)	6.15	46.4 ± 2.4	-144 ± 8	21
$[\text{Cr}(\text{Salm})(\text{OH}_2)_2]^+/\text{N}_3^-$	11.5 (25 °C)	4.35	63.1 ± 3.2	-73 ± 22	21
$[\text{Cr}(\text{Salm})(\text{OH}_2)_2]^+/\text{SCN}^-$	18.9 (25 °C)	3.16	70.6 ± 7.2	-96 ± 9.5	21
$[\text{Cr}(\text{Salm})(\text{OH}_2)_2]^+/\text{py}$	14.5 (25 °C)	6.70	63.1 ± 3.2	-169 ± 16	21
$[\text{Cr}(\text{Salm})(\text{OH}_2)_2]^+/\text{pyc-2}$	17.6 (25 °C)	8.75	40.7 ± 4.8	-201 ± 0.6	21
$[\text{Cr}(\text{Salm})(\text{OH}_2)_2]^+/\text{pyc-3}$	18.8 (25 °C)	3.00	28.3 ± 0.2	-172 ± 19	21
$[\text{Cr}(\text{Salm})(\text{OH}_2)_2]^+/\text{Gly}$	14.98 (25 °C)	4.39	57.74 ± 1.76	-104.67 ± 5.02	This work
$[\text{Cr}(\text{Salm})(\text{OH}_2)_2]^+/\text{Ile}$	8.45 (25 °C)	4.15	38.35 ± 1.34	-175.1 ± 4.7	This work
$[\text{Cr}(\text{Salm})(\text{OH}_2)_2]^+/\text{Paba}$	10.52 (25 °C)	8.20	43.05 ± 0.8	-157.1 ± 2.8	This work
$[\text{Cr}(\text{Salm})(\text{OH}_2)_2]^+/\text{His}$	14.23 (25 °C)	2.50	34.23 ± 2.67	-65.8 ± 9	This work
$[\text{Cr}(\text{Salm})(\text{OH}_2)_2]^+/\text{Gly-gly}$	13.78 (25 °C)	5.21	39.72 ± 3.14	-166.15 ± 11.43	This work

^agly = glycine, ala = alanine, val = valine, Imz = imidazole, pyc-3 = pyridine-3 carboxylic acid, pyc-2 = pyridine-2-carboxylic acid, Ile = isoleucine, Paba = *p* aminobenzoic acid, His = histidine, Gly-gly = glycyl-glycine

and K_{OS} compare well with the values reported for similar reacting species. The small variation of k_{an} values also suggest that substitution at (aqua) Cr^{III} centre is sensitive to nature of nucleophile and hence support an I_a mechanism²⁰. The negative values of ΔS^\ddagger with moderate values of ΔH^\ddagger are typical for Cr^{III} substitution with an associative mechanism^{23–27}. Further, a plot of ΔS^\ddagger vs ΔH^\ddagger of relevant systems (see Table 3) with those derived for the present study resulted in an isokinetic relationship which further supports I_a mechanism.

Experimental

Materials and methods

In a typical lot a mixture of concentrated methanolic solution of H_2Salm , aqueous solution of $\text{Cr}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and lithium hydroxide in the molar ratio 1 : 1 : 5 were taken in a conical flask and refluxed at 80 °C for 5 h.

The resulting solution was evaporated to a small volume which on cooling yielded the desired complex as bright green solid. The crude complex was re-crystallized from methanol-water mixture. The complex is readily soluble in methanol-water mixture (MeOH = 10% v/v) at ambient temperature. The melting point of the complex is found to be 275 °C²¹.

Conclusion

trans- $[\text{Cr}(\text{Salm})(\text{OH}_2)_2]\text{NO}_3$, derived from the reaction of *N,N*-ethylene-bis-salicylamide (H_2Salm) and $\text{Cr}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, exhibits hydrolysis of only one aqua ligand in the pH range of 5–11. The reaction of *trans*- $[\text{Cr}(\text{Salm})(\text{OH}_2)_2]^+$ with several biologically important nucleophiles revealed one aqua ligand substitution at about 10^3 times faster than the water exchange rate at $[\text{Cr}(\text{OH}_2)_6]^{3+}$ centre. The rate and activation parameters support an I_a mechanism for the substitution reaction.

Acknowledgement

The author SCD is thankful to University Grants Commission, New Delhi and Principal of Nimapara College, Nimapara (Puri) for study leave.

References

1. D. Chatterjee, A. Mitra, M. S. A. Hamza and R. van Eldik, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 2002, 962 and references therein.
2. W. Zeng, J. Li and S. Qin, *Inorg. Chem. Commun.*, 2006, 9, 10.
3. L. Dyers (Jr.), S. Y. Que, D. van Derveer and X. R. Bu, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2006, 359, 197.
4. K. G. Gupta, H. K. Abdusikadir and S. Chand, *J. Mol. Catal. (A)*, 2003, 202, 253.
5. Y. Luo and J. Lin, *Micropor. Mesopor. Mater.*, 2005, 86, 23.
6. V. D. Chaube, S. Shylesh and A. P. Singh, *J. Mol. Catal. (A)*, 2005, 241, 79.
7. J.-Y. Liu, Y.-S. Li, J.-Y. Liu and Z.-S. Li, *J. Mol. Catal. (A) : Chem.*, 2005, 244, 99.
8. V. G. Vaidyanathan, T. Weyhennuller, B. U. Nair and J. Subramanian, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 2005, 99, 2248.
9. F. Bedioui, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1995, 144, 39 and references therein.
10. P. V. Bernhardt, F. Bozoglian, B. P. Macpherson and M. Martinez, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2003, 249, 1902.
11. M. R. Maurya, S. J. J. Titinchi, S. Chand and I. M. Mishra, *J. Mol. Catal. (A) : Chem.*, 2002, 180, 201; M. R. Maurya, S. J. J. Titinchi and S. Chand, *J. Mol. Catal. (A) : Chem.*, 2004, 214, 257.
12. H. Zhang, S. Xiang, J. Xiao and C. Li, *J. Mol. Catal. (A) : Chem.*, 2005, 238, 175 and references therein.
13. H. Y. Shrivastava and B. Unni Nair, *Biochem. Biophys. Res. Commun.*, 2000, 270, 749.
14. H. Y. Shrivastava, T. Ravikumar, N. Shanmugasundaram, M. Babu and B. Unni Nair, *Free Rad. Biol. Med.*, 2005, 38, 58.
15. S. S. Mandal, N. V. Kumar, U. Varshney and S. Bhattacharya, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 1996, 63, 265.
16. M. Kanthimathi and B. Unni Nair, *Trans. Met. Chem*, 2004, 29, 751.
17. D. R. Prasad, T. Ramasami, D. Ramaswamy and M. Santappa, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1982, 21, 850.
18. K. R. Ashley, J. G. Leipoldt and V. K. Joshi, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1980, 19, 1608.
19. J. G. Leipoldt and H. Mayer, *Polyhedron*, 1987, 6, 1387.
20. M. L. Tobe and J. Burgess, "Inorganic Reaction Mechanism", Longman, Edinburgh Gate Harlow, England, 1997.
21. S. C. Dash, G. S. Brahma, R. Das, N. N. Das and P. Mohanty, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2006, 45, 2406.
22. R. B. Jordan, "Reaction Mechanism of Inorganic and Organa Metallic Systems", Oxford University Press, New York, 1991.
23. S. K. Bhattacharya and R. N. Banerjee, *Polyhedron*, 1997, 16, 4217.
24. I. A. Khan and Kabir-ud-Din, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 1985, 17, 1263.
25. I. A. Khan, Kabir-ud-Din and M. Sahid, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1992, 69, 864; *Transition Met Chem.*, 1987, 12, 293, 557; I. A. Khan, M. Shahid and Kabir-ud-Din, *Z. Phys Chem. (Leipzig)*, 1990, 27, 101.
26. S. Mohanty, S. Anand, G. S. Brahma and P. Mohanty, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2003, 80, 810.
27. J. Behera, G. S. Brahma and P. Mohanty, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2001, 78, 125.

